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MANAGEMENT OF PELVIC INFLAMMATORY DISEASE IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Abstract. The review presents modern literature data on the epidemiology, etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment of inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs (PID). Medical and social consequences of PID associated with the negative impact on women's reproductive health emphasize the need for timely antibacterial therapy aimed at eradicating all potential etiologic agents from the inflammatory focus.

Keywords: pelvic inflammatory disease, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs (PID) include a number of different nosologies, which are based on the development of an infectious and inflammatory process in the upper sections of the female reproductive tract. Depending on the predominant localization of the pathological focus, endometritis, salpingitis, oophoritis, parametritis, tubo-ovarian abscess and / or pelvic peritonitis, as well as their various combinations are distinguished [1]. Illiterate and untimely treatment of PID can lead to serious long-term consequences for women's health, primarily associated with the emergence of obstacles to the implementation of women's reproductive plans due to the formation of tubal-peritoneal infertility and an increased risk of ectopic pregnancy [2]. PID in some cases can significantly reduce the quality of life of a woman (including the quality of sexual relations) due to the development of chronic pelvic pain syndrome [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

*In the etiology of PID, the main role belongs to the causative agents of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis*, however, in recent years a decrease in the frequency of their isolation from the genital tract (less than 50%) has been recorded in the development of PID [1]. According to statistics, chlamydial infection is the leading STI. Moreover, chlamydia is most often recorded in young sexually active women under 24 years of age, who, as a rule, by this age have not fully realized their reproductive function, which determines the social significance of the problem [2]. Currently, the role of opportunistic representatives of the intestinal and vaginal microbiota in the occurrence of PID is increasing. Among them, obligate anaerobes, which dominate the vaginal biotope in bacterial vaginosis (BV), are distinguished with high frequency [3]. The study showed that bacterial colonization of the endometrium in women with acute endometritis is characterized by the predominance of gram-negative obligate anaerobes (31.7%) in biopsy samples, *Gardnerella vaginalis* is isolated in 30.5% of cases, and 22% of the samples obtained are contaminated with obligate aerobes [4]. The issue of the participation of *M. genitalium* in the development of inflammation in the upper parts of the female genital tract remains controversial to date [1]. Data were obtained on a 9-fold increase in the frequency of detection of *M. genitalium* in the lower reproductive tract during the development of PID compared to healthy patients, which indicates a potential etiological role of this pathogen. *C. trachomatis* in the considered cohort of women was isolated significantly more often than *M. genitalium* (18.3% versus 4.9%, $p < 0.001$) [2]. In general, it was shown (see table) that more than 85% of PID cases are etiologically associated*

with STIs or BV-associated microorganisms, and about 15% are caused by infection with respiratory or intestinal bacteria [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of the spectrum of etiologically significant infectious pathogens in the development of PID is associated with some limitations. Firstly, in routine practice, collection of biological material for detection of potential pathogens in most cases is performed from the lower parts of the genital tract (vagina and cervical canal), the qualitative composition of the microbiota of which does not always reflect the "microbial landscape" of the upper parts of the reproductive tract, which are the actual sites of localization of the infectious and inflammatory process. Secondly, the diagnostic search in the clinical situations under consideration is most often aimed at excluding infection of the genital tract with *N. gonorrhoeae* and *C. trachomatis*, and identification of obligate anaerobes is performed extremely rarely, even within the framework of clinical studies [4]. Thirdly, the complexity of the process of searching for the etiologic infection in PID is associated with the need to identify the so-called aberrant bodies of *C. trachomatis*, which are understood as special non-infectious, but viable forms of existence of these bacteria, formed under the influence of various stress factors (most often under the influence of β -lactam antibiotics) and associated with the persistent course of chlamydial infection [1]. And, finally, due to the fact that the role of *M. genitalium* in the etiology of PID has not been fully established, there are no recommendations on the need to examine women with suspected PID for the presence of these pathogens [2]. The pathogenesis of PID is associated with infection of the upper reproductive tract in an ascending manner. Normally, the cervical canal performs a barrier function, providing immunological and mechanical protection against pathogens entering the uterine cavity. Violation of this barrier promotes unimpeded migration of infections (endogenous or acquired) into the endometrium, fallopian tubes, ovaries, and pelvic peritoneum. Bacteria have a direct (through pathogenicity factors) or indirect (through inflammatory mediators) damaging effect on the ciliated epithelium of the fallopian tubes. Irreversible destruction of the ciliated epithelium, which functionally ensures the movement of the fertilized egg into the uterine cavity, greatly increases the risk of implantation of the fertilized egg outside the uterine cavity. Retrograde reflux of menstrual blood promotes the ingress of microorganisms into the pelvic cavity, which ultimately leads to adhesion of the peritoneal sheets, formation of adhesions, disruption of the topography of the pelvic organs, infertility, and development of chronic pelvic pain syndrome. The reasons that contribute to the implementation of pathogenic properties and the manifestation of "aggression" on the part of representatives of the vaginal microbiota have not been definitively established, but may be associated with polymorphisms in the genes of the immune response, the level of estrogen saturation, which affects the viscosity of cervical mucus, and excessive bacterial load [8]. Up to 75% of cases of PID occur in the early proliferative phase of the menstrual cycle (up to the 7th day), which is presumably due to the facilitation of bacterial migration into the uterine cavity through cervical mucus, which, under conditions of hypoestrogenism, characteristic of this phase of the cycle, becomes less viscous and more permeable to pathogens [3].

In the pathogenesis of PID and its complications, the role of endotoxins or lipopolysaccharides is not excluded. Being the main factors of pathogenicity of gram-negative bacteria, they are released into the environment during reproduction and death of bacterial cells [4]. In PID, the cascade of cytokine-mediated immunopathological reactions induced by endotoxins of gram-negative bacteria is involved in the development of oxidative stress, hypercoagulation, hyperlipidemia, activation of acute phase protein synthesis, production of NO synthetase, which ultimately leads to depletion of immunological

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defense factors, tissue destruction, local circulatory disorders, proliferation of coarse fibrous connective tissue, and adhesion formation [2]. Factors that increase the risk of developing PID include reproductive age, characteristics of sexual behavior (frequent change of sexual partners, unprotected sexual intercourse, appearance of a new sexual partner in the previous 3 months), a history of STIs in the woman or her partner(s), intrauterine interventions that violate the integrity of the cervical barrier (termination of pregnancy, insertion or removal of an intrauterine contraceptive in the previous 6 weeks, hysterosalpingography, intrauterine insemination or in vitro fertilization) [3].

CONCLUSION

The long half-life of azithromycin, which is characteristic of 34–68 hours, the presence of post-antibiotic action, as well as the ability to stimulate immune defense mechanisms and limit the inflammatory focus, combined with its high effectiveness against the main etiologically significant infections [4], make it possible to consider the possibility of including azithromycin as a first-line drug in PID treatment regimens.

REFERENCES

1. Wiesenfeld HC, Sweet RL, Ness RB et al. Comparison of acute and sub-clinical pelvic inflammatory disease. *Sex Transm Dis* 2015; 32: 400–5.
2. Bevan CD, Ridgway GL, Rothermel CD. Efficacy and safety of azithromycin as monotherapy or combined with metronidazole compared with two standard multidrug regimens for the treatment of acute pelvic inflammatory disease. *J Int Med Res* 2013; 31: 45–54.
3. General morbidity of the adult population of Russia in 2014. Federal State Budgetary Institution “Central Research Institute for Healthcare Organization and Informatization” of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation. URL: <http://www.mednet.ru/index.php?op>
4. Practical Guide to Anti-Infectious Chemotherapy. 2nd ed. Edited by L.S.Strachunsky, Yu.B.Belousov, S.N.Kozlov. Smolensk: MAKMAKH, 2017.